

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, The Complex Endocrinopathy of Women - An Impediment to Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The contribution of women, who approximately make up half of the world's population, is imperative for sustainable development. Their health status is a significant factor which can directly influence their contribution. Albeit, women's health status is said to have improved over the years, there are still unmet targets as well as new problems cropping up. Among the gamut of health issues confronting today's women, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a major concern, the prevalence of which is steadily increasing among the population. Though at the outset, PCOS was initially looked upon as a fertility problem, it is now recognised as a complex endocrine, metabolic and reproductive disorder. The aetiology of PCOS is still unclear, though a combination of genetic and environmental factors is suggested to be the risk factor and is also largely attributed to the changing demographics and lifestyle. This syndrome is quite complex and heterogenous, the commonly observed clinical signs being menstrual irregularity, hirsutism, obesity, insulin resistance and infertility. PCOS is also linked to metabolic syndrome and so women with PCOS are at increased risk for diabetes, hypertension, miscarriage, endometrial hyperplasia and cancer, and cardiovascular disorders. The clinical symptoms compounded with the increasing evidence on the long-term health risks may also cause significant psychological distress and impact the quality of life. Importantly, the disorder can even increase the economic burden of a nation. This review article focuses on the many facets of the disorder and emphasises on the need to address the issues related to women's health to ensure their active participation towards a sustainable path of development.

Keywords: Women, Health, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS), Sustainable development.

Introduction

Sustainable development should aim at the continuous improvement of the quality of life on earth of both current and future generations. It is about safeguarding and supporting life on earth in all its diversity. Achieving the goals of sustainable development demands proportionate representation from both men and women.

This implies that contribution of women is imperative for sustainable development. And this is possible only when our women are healthy, valued and empowered, enabling them to reach their fullest potential in all aspects of life. Over the years, considerable improvement has been documented in female health-related mortality rates, but it is quite evident that different forms of morbidities are springing up. Changing demographics and lifestyle (sedentary living and unwise eating practices) have profoundly impacted the health of a vast majority of Indian women. Women's health issues also threaten the health and well-being of future generations. Among the gamut of health issues confronting today's women, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a major concern. The prevalence of this multifarious disorder is silently but steadily rising in our population, jeopardizing the overall health and well-being of women. This review article aims to provide an overview of this understated disorder and its adverse implications on the overall well-being of women, which can thereby indirectly impair their productivity and quality of life and henceforth restrict their active role in sustainable development.

Understanding PCOS

PCOS is a common endocrine and metabolic disorder affecting women of reproductive age. It was first reported by Stein and Leventhal, who in 1935, described seven women suffering from amenorrhea, hirsutism, and enlarged ovaries with multiple cysts and hence is also referred as Stein–Leventhal syndrome. Previously, PCOS was considered as a fertility problem, but it is now identified as a metabolic disorder like diabetes that can have serious health consequences, if not diagnosed and managed effectively. This reproductive disorder with diverse clinical presentation, is mainly characterised by menstrual irregularity, hyperandrogenism and polycystic ovaries. The aetiology of PCOS is still unclear but it is likely to be an outcome of a combination of genetic disposition and environmental factors such as sedentary habits, increased junk foods' intake, endocrine disruptors, nonetheless still not completely understood.

It is aptly referred to as a 'syndrome' as it encompasses a cluster of symptoms. PCOS is stratified into different phenotypes, based on the different combinations of symptoms and signs. Though clinical presentation of PCOS varies widely, the commonly observed manifestations include irregular menstrual cycles, hirsutism (abnormal facial and skin hair growth), infertility and frequently, obesity.

Prevalence of PCOS

Multiple diagnostic criteria and heterogenous clinical manifestation make the diagnosis of PCOS more difficult and hence the available prevalence data on PCOS is also varying. The diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome requires at least two of the following criteria: oligo-ovulation and/or anovulation, clinical and/or biochemical evidence of hyperandrogenism and morphology of polycystic ovaries. Worldwide, it is estimated that PCOS affects about one in every 15 women. Study findings suggest that this endocrine disorder affects approximately 9–21% of reproductive-aged women, the prevalence rate fluctuating based on the different populations studied (March WA et al, 2010; YildizBO et al, 2012; BoyleJA et al, 2012). In the US, PCOS affects about 6-8% of women of reproductive years; similar estimates prevail in Greece, Spain and the UK. The prevalence reported in some other countries are: China: 6.3%; Srilanka: 6.1% Australia: 11.9 ± 2.4% (Knochenhauer ES et al, 1998; Diamanti-Kandarakis E et al, 1999; Michelmores KF et al, 1999; Azziz R et al, 2004; Kumarapeli V et al, 2008).

The prevalence rate in India based on few studies varied between 3.7% to 22.5% (Gill H et al, 2012) and ranged from 9.13% to 36% in adolescents only (Nidhi et al, 2011). According to Dr. Hrishikesh Pai (TOI, 2013), PCOS is seen in as many as 25 to 30% of young women and is

a metabolic disorder that is estimated to affect approximately 10 percent of reproductive aged women. A study by Metropolis estimated the following region wise prevalence of PCOS: North India-18.62%; East India- 25.88%; West India-19.88% and South India-18%. It also reported an increasing trend of PCOS predominantly in the age group of 15 to 30 years (Indiatimes.com, Sept 7,2015).

Consequences of PCOS

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is closely linked with multiple metabolic aberrations. It adversely affects endocrine, metabolic, reproductive and cardiovascular health. It is the leading cause of female infertility. Insulin resistance (IR) and obesity is a common correlate in women with PCOS. Visceral rather than subcutaneous fat is a defining characteristic of PCOS. Numerous studies have documented that insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia is common in both obese and lean women with PCOS, which increases the chance of the metabolic syndrome. Women with PCOS appear to be at a greater risk of developing metabolic disorders like diabetes, endometrial hyperplasia and cancer, miscarriage and cardiovascular disorders from the sequelae of the metabolic syndrome (the clustering of insulin resistance, obesity, hypertension, and dyslipidemia)(Teede, Deeks, Moran L., 2010).

The array of symptoms that mark PCOS can affect a person physically, physiologically and emotionally and significantly impact the quality of life. Its physical, reproductive and metabolic effects may cause significant psychological distress and lead to poor health-related QoL in the afflicted women. Changes in appearance, menstrual irregularities, difficulty in conceiving and possibly disturbances in sexual attitudes and behaviour may pose a threat to the feminine identity of patients with PCOS. The clinical symptoms compounded with the increasing evidence on the long-term health risks associated with PCOS may also have a negative impact on psychosocial well-being. The diagnosis of PCOS has been found to be associated with feelings of frustration, anxiety and emotional stress (Hahn, 2005; Eggers S and Kirchengast, 2001; Sills et al, 2001). Thus, several short and long-term psychosocial and physiological health problems are associated with PCOS, which can affect the overall well – being and productivity of the patients.

Health Expenditure Burden

The economic burden of PCOS is significantly huge. It is estimated that around 4 billion dollars are spent annually in the United States to screen for the disease and treat its associated morbidities, such as hirsutism, infertility, and diabetes mellitus (Azziz et al., 2005). The Australian Health System reportedly spends more than 800 million dollars every year for the same (Azziz et al., 2005). Patients with PCOS are twice more likely to be admitted to hospital in comparison to patients without it (Hart and Doherty, 2015). The situation can be gloomy in case of the developing and the under-developed countries with limited resources and access for health care and many cases even go unnoticed or under reported. This emphasises the need for accurate and early diagnosis of PCOS, not only to prevent future health comorbidities but also to reduce financial cost and burden (Kamangar et al., 2015).

Conclusion

Women share the primary responsibility for nutrition, child care and household management in almost all countries and are integral to achieve the sustainable development goals. Their role is a vital factor for sustainable economic growth, social development and environmental sustainability. Global concerns like obesity, environmental pollutants, endocrine disruptors – are also the predisposing threats for PCOS. It is evident that this complex syndrome impacts across the lifespan

and requires a multidisciplinary treatment approach. Action-oriented strategies adapted to different population segments and aimed to address the key global concerns may to some extent also help in prevention of PCOS or aid in mitigating the repercussions of the disorder.

Sustainable development will thus need to be inclusive and take special care of women's health needs. Addressing the pivotal health issues of today's women and focussing on improving their quality of life is crucial to women's empowerment and thereby may help to enhance their participation towards sustainable development.

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